

Pattern-Based Algebraic Approximation of $\cos\left(\frac{\pi}{n}\right)$

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Abstract

I derive an algebraic function from an observed geometric pattern that serves as an approximation to $\cos\left(\frac{\pi}{n}\right)$. The proposed approximation is given by

$$P(n) = \frac{1}{2^{\frac{1}{n-2}}}$$

Numerical evaluation indicates that $P(n)$ provides a level of accuracy suitable for algebraic manipulation in the domain $\{2\} \cup [3, \infty)$ with error reaching the most of 3%. I emphasize that this expression is intended as an approximation and does not represent the exact value of the trigonometric function.

1 Introduction

Trigonometric functions are a significant part mathematics, also playing a crucial role in physics, engineering, etc; however our inability to manually find a value for them makes it hard to use them hence many algebraic expansions such as Taylor approximation and polynomial interpolation.

The approximations are used in both theoretical and practical fields, hence different approximations can be used for different criteria.

In this work, an alternative algebraic approximation to the function $\cos(\pi/x)$ is proposed, derived from an observed in the geometric pattern of a regular polygon formed from another polygons mid-points having the same number of sides as the original.

the aim of this paper is not to obtain an exact representation of the trigonometric function, but rather to provide an approximation for easier computation. Numerical evidence supporting the effectiveness is presented.

2 Derivation of the Approximation

From vector addition of side of the polygon we get each side formed from the mid-point of the greater polygon having sides of length a the smaller side will

Figure 1: Regular Square

be:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sqrt{\frac{a^2}{2} + \frac{a^2}{2} + 2 \frac{a}{2} \frac{a}{2} \cos\left(\frac{(n-2)\pi}{n}\right)} \\
 &= \sqrt{\frac{a^2}{2} + \frac{a^2}{2} \cos\left(\frac{(n-2)\pi}{n}\right)} \\
 &= \frac{a}{\sqrt{2}} \sqrt{1 + \cos\left(\frac{(n-2)\pi}{n}\right)} \\
 &= \frac{a}{\sqrt{2}} \sqrt{2 \sin^2\left(\frac{(n-2)\pi}{2n}\right)} \\
 &= a \sin\left(\frac{(n-2)\pi}{2n}\right) \\
 &= a \sin\left(\frac{n\pi}{2n} - \frac{2\pi}{2n}\right) \\
 &= a \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \frac{2\pi}{2n}\right) \\
 &= a \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{2n}\right) \\
 &= a \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{n}\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, the ratio of the new polygons side to the originals is $a \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{n}\right) : a$ ∴ total change is $\cos\left(\frac{\pi}{n}\right)$

but if we take an equilateral triangle the sides each are a then from basic proportionality theorem we get that the length of the smaller sides of the triangle $a/2$ which mean the ratio is 1:2, In a square of sides a we see that the new sides are $a/\sqrt{2}$ which can be written as $a/2^{1/2}$ and the ratio being $1:2^{1/2}$ hence we can see that for $n=3$ (triangle) the ratio is $1:2^{\frac{1}{3-2}}$ and for $n=4$ (square) the ratio is $1:2^{\frac{1}{4-2}}$ further data is given below

As we see there is a error of 0.03 or 3%

Table 1: Comparison of $\cos(\pi/n)$ and its approximation $P(n)$

n	$\cos(\pi/n)$	$P(n)$	Taylor expansion until 10 terms
2	0	0	0
3	$\frac{1}{2}$	$\frac{1}{2}$	$\frac{1}{2}$
4	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$
5	0.80	0.79	0.80
7	0.90	0.87	0.90
11	0.95	0.92	0.95
13	0.97	0.94	0.97
20	0.98	0.96	0.98
50	0.99	0.98	0.99
100	0.99	0.99	0.99

Figure 2: $\cos(\frac{\pi}{n})VSP(n)$ graph

3 Error Analysis

For $n \geq 2$, both $\cos(\frac{\pi}{n})$ and its approximation $P(n)$ attain a minimum value of 0 at $n = 2$. As $n \rightarrow \infty$, both functions increase monotonically and approach 1. Hence, the supremum is 1, while no maximum exists.

Due to the monotonic behavior the relative error can range between positive and negative values though the most stable value lie in the domain $2 \cup [3, \infty)$ that following domain has very little error as compared to the rest of real numbers

4 Conclusion

In this work, a simple approximation for $\cos(\pi/n)$ was proposed and compared with its exact values for integer $n \geq 2$. Numerical comparison shows that the

approximation follows the same behavior as $\cos(\pi/n)$, matching exactly for small values of n and remaining close for larger n . Both the exact function and the approximation attain a minimum value of 0 at $n = 2$ and approach 1 as n increases, indicating similar limiting behavior.

This approximation is empirical and is not presented as a rigorous derivation. Its purpose is to highlight an observable numerical pattern rather than to replace exact trigonometric expressions. Further work could focus on analyzing the approximation error, improving accuracy for smaller and negative n , or exploring whether a formal derivation or tighter bound can be established.